

RECONSTRUCTION OF ORBITAL FLOOR FRACTURE WITH TITANIUM IMPLANTS**Petkov D.**

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ABSTRACT

Aim: The purpose of this study is to evaluate the use of titanium mesh as a reconstruction material in cases of orbital blowout fractures, and its advantages. **Methods:** This study was conducted at the university hospital Burgas, Bulgaria from February 2021 to January 2023. All the cases were operated on in 24 months. The recorded data included age, gender, and cause of trauma. **Results:** 14 of 20 were males and 6 were females. Motor vehicle accident was the most common cause of trauma, aggression was the second cause. All patients with enophthalmos or ocular motility disorders improved. No patients required reoperation. **Conclusion:** Titanium mesh was highly effective for the sealing of orbital wall defects and improvement of symptoms, with no major complications. Titanium mesh is a good orbital reconstruction material.

Keywords: titanium implants, orbital blowout fractures, reconstruction.

INTRODUCTION

Orbital blowout fractures are one of the most challenging injuries in the management of maxillofacial trauma. The term 'blow-out fracture' was coined in 1957, when Smith and Regan[1] described the mechanism of injury. They produced an impact on the orbital soft tissues, increasing hydraulic pressure, and causing the thin, internal walls to fracture. Soft tissues were displaced or incarcerated, correlating with enophthalmos and restricted motility. Fujino later disputed this theory and proposed that a direct compression force or buckling force transmitted via the orbital rim was the causative factor for orbital floor fractures[2]. This theory of bone conduction or 'tsunami' mechanism of injury was first proposed by LeFort and Lagrange at the turn of the century. Erling et al recently resurrected an older theory on the etiology of orbital fractures that was first described by Pfeiffer in 1943. They proposed that the responsible mechanism of fracture is direct globe-to-wall contact; i.e. posterior movement of the globe, in response to an external force, results in a fracture upon direct contact.[3,4]

Orbital fractures account for 30% to 55% of all facial fractures. The most frequent etiology varies according to gender: in men, these fractures are more frequently the result of aggression, whereas, in women, the most frequent cause is an accidental fall. Fractures can be classified differently according to the degree of displacement, the degree of gravity and the fracture pattern, the degree of segmentation and comminution, and the strength applied against the bone, as well as according to the combination of their location, the number of fragments and the soft tissues affected [5,6].

According to a manuscript published in 2003, the ability of titanium mesh to conform to the contours of the orbit makes it a better material for reconstructing not only isolated floor fractures but also those defects that involve both the floor and medial wall, and this is partially based on the finding that many of the bone grafts used are too thick: decreasing orbital volume compared with the uninjured side and also elevating the floor in the anterior orbit creates an adverse effect elevating the globe.[7]

The most commonly noted features of orbital blowout fractures include periorbital edema, subconjunctival hemorrhage, diplopia, enophthalmos, extraocular muscle entrapment, and restriction of eye movement. Indications for surgery can be enophthalmos (>2 mm), extraocular muscle entrapment with diplopia, large floor fractures (>50%), and oculocardiac reflex.[8]

The goal of treatment is a restoration of the anatomic and functional defects of the globe. Recently, numerous approaches for the reduction of orbital floor fractures have been proposed including transorbital, transantral, and transnasal using endoscopy. Various materials have been introduced to cover the floor defect or support the prolapsed orbital contents from the maxillary sinus [9].

MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study was conducted at the university hospital Burgas, Bulgaria from February 2021 to January 2023. All the cases were operated on in 24 months.

All the patients underwent a complete ENT examination. CT scan was done in all cases. All patients were systematically evaluated and investigated to rule out any contraindications for surgery under general anesthesia.

All the patients were operated on under general anesthesia. A forced duction test was performed at the beginning. The pupillary response was checked at frequent intervals. Other associated fractures were reduced before orbital floor exploration. Traditionally, the orbital floor is accessed transcutaneously via infra-orbital or via preexisting lacerations. Starting soft tissue dissection up to the infraorbital rim, opening periosteum and subperiosteal dissection deep to the orbital floor, deep in the orbit a malleable retractor is used to elevate the orbital tissues and improve visibility to properly identify the orbital fracture defect, reduction of the herniated orbital contents from side to side to avoid penetration of the orbital tissues. A titanium mesh was placed to achieve overcorrection of the globe position.

The final angulation between the anterior portion of the mesh used for fixation and the "intraorbital" por-

tion of the mesh supporting the globe was closely tailored to achieve a slight overcorrection of the globe position. The mesh was fixed with one titanium screw at the inferior orbital rim. An incision was closed in layers.

RESULTS

Sex and age of the patients:

In this study, 20 patients (14 males and 6 females; age, 18–83 years; mean age, 43.6 years) with unilateral orbital floor underwent orbital restoration surgery using a titanium mesh plate. The majority of patients were male (70%). Among the etiological factors, the most prevalent were related to means of transport, comprising 55% of the studied population, followed by physical aggression with 25%, and falls with 20% fractures. There were (65%) simple facial fractures (a single fracture in the face) and (35%) multiple facial fractures. Indications for orbital fracture repair included medium to large fractures of one or more walls, and comminuted or non-comminuted displaced orbital rims. The average surgical timing was 8.2 days after the injury (range, 9–33 days). There were no intraoperative complications such as damage to the globe or the optic nerve or unexpected hemorrhage.

There were no postoperative complications like bleeding, vision loss, infection, and implant extrusion. No vision loss or decline occurred in any patients post-operation. None of the patients showed any clinical foreign-body reactions. There was no evidence of infection.

DISCUSSION

Management of complex orbital fracture includes accurate orbital margin reduction, anatomic reconstruction of orbital wall, and fulfillment of intraorbital contents[10]. The surgeon can adjust the curvature of titanium mesh to reduce orbital volume instead of increasing fulfilling contents. Accurate reduction of the orbital margin is fundamental to the anatomic reconstructions of the orbital wall, which can be favorably conducted by titanium plate and nail fixation after orbital margin reduction[11]. Attention should be paid to orbital wall reconstruction. The incision should be made at the orbital margin to excise the periosteum; tissues should be separated under the periosteum while maintaining its intact; herniated tissues should be reduced after exposing the fracture site to release extraocular muscle compression. Concerning the materials, titanium mesh can be easily fixed with little incidence of slippage.

However, titanium mesh is hard and iatrogenic injury is likely to occur if it is not appropriately implanted[12]. We use titanium mesh to repair orbital wall defects and a titanium plate to repair fractures of the orbital margin. Consequently, no complication of iatrogenic injury, infection, discharging, and displacement was reported. The transorbital approach is currently regarded as the mainstream method for the reduction of blowout fractures of the inferior orbital wall. Titanium has good biocompatibility, strength, and osteointegration properties. It is radio-opaque and has been successfully used for craniomaxillofacial osteosynthesis for several decades. A pre-contoured titanium mesh is pre-cut and contoured to mimic the native orbital anatomy based on normative data and adult skull

models. It can be easily trimmed to the required size and permits easy and quick contouring while maintaining its shape once contoured. It also provides plenty of options for fixation depending on individual fracture patterns. This allows precise volume restoration, saves operative time, and eliminates donor site morbidity.[13]

Tang et al used rapid prototyping and titanium mesh reconstruction to achieve orbital volumes within 2% of the uninjured side; however, 16/41 (34%) subjects still had persistent enophthalmos. [14]

The present study showed that complex orbital fracture had male predominance (70%), and the traffic accident (55%) is a leading cause. This result is under the report of Gear et al[15] In contrast, Hwang et al[16] reported that although the fracture had male predominance, the leading cause was fighting, followed by a traffic accident. But, as Hwang et al analyzed the causes based on orbital fractures caused by both simple blow-out fractures and complex fractures instead of separating complex orbital fractures, the results are not contradictory.

Concerning the timing of the surgery, most authors propose early surgical intervention[17]. Early intervention can reduce the herniated soft tissue back into a normal position, thereby reducing the incidence of ischemia, scar-forming, necrosis, and atrophy of intraorbital soft tissues and facilitating recovery of the appearance and function. If the operation is conducted later, soft tissues around the orbit may adhere extensively, showing scar formation and atrophy.

CONCLUSION

The orbital wall is one of the most frequently damaged parts of the maxillofacial skeleton after midfacial trauma. Regardless of the fracture site, blowout fractures can cause various functional and aesthetic sequelae. Blowout fractures are one of the most challenging injuries in the management of maxillofacial trauma. Despite significant advances in our understanding of these injuries, a universal "ideal" reconstructive material remains elusive. We have attempted to elaborate on our experience with pre-contoured mesh, which restores orbital wall anatomy, is safe, quick, fairly easy, and reproducible with a shorter learning curve. According to our work, we found it can be adapted to complex structures easily, and it can also be cut to shape as well. Proper patient selection and execution, pre-contoured titanium mesh can serve as an excellent reconstructive option in blowout fractures of the orbit.

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